

African Geothermal Play Types ; Typology for Identification ; Development Approach

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ABSTRACT

Africa is still a continent where geothermal energy opportunities remain unknown or ill developed. There is no specific geothermal system in Africa, and it is of use to precise the various possible options. In this perspective, is proposed to distinguish 10 geothermal play-types based on the geodynamic environments encountered in Africa:

- 1: Eastern branch of the East African Rift System;
- 2: Red-Sea and Gulf of Aden including Afar;
- 3: Western branch of the East African Rift System and Southern Rifts;
- 4: Deep reservoirs from sedimentary basins;
- 5: North Africa (Mediterranean collision zone);
- 6: Oceanic and continental mantle plumes (Comoros, Cap Verde, Darfur);
- 7: Oceanic fracture zones off-shore & on land (Cameroon line);
- 8: hot-springs & heat anomalies from basement discontinuities;
- 9: Deep EGS;
- 10: Ground Heat Pumps (12-24°C average).

Each play-type is defined and reported on the map of Africa, allowing to illustrate the specific geothermal conceptual model defined by the corresponding geological parameters (volcanic, sedimentary, tectonic, etc...). Each play types also allows for a specific geothermal application, with rather different economic characteristics. The exploration strategy also differs, and is précised for each play-type, and the same for kind of development and technology to be considered. And of course, the social approach of each play type, and the kind of stakeholders and developers to be involved need to be adjusted to each case. It is hoped that this contribution will help promoting ad-hoc geothermal development in Africa based on both the geothermal resource characteristics and the associated social demand at the surface.

1. Introduction

Geothermal Energy offers Africa various perspectives but these are still unknown or lacking development. There is no specific geothermal system in the continent, and it is of use to identify the various possible options. In this perspective, it is proposed to distinguish 10 geothermal play-types based on their geodynamic environments (Figure 1).

Each play-type is defined and reported on the geological map of Africa, allowing to illustrate the specific geothermal conceptual model based on the specific geological parameters characterizing each play type. Each play types in fact allows for specific geothermal applications with rather different economic perspective. The nature of the risk and the exploration strategy will differ, and the same for kind of development and technology to be considered for each play-type. The social approach and the kind of stakeholders and developers to be involved also need to be adjusted to each case.

The aim of this contribution is to help promoting ad-hoc geothermal development in Africa based on both the geothermal resource characteristics and the associated social demand at the surface.

N°	Geodynamic context	Location	Geothermal play type	Geothermal application	Exploration strategy	Developer considered
1	Eastern branch of the East African Rift System		volcano hosted high enthalpy systems	electricity production	3 stages approach	public enterprises / private investors
2	Red-Sea and Gulf of Aden including Afar		active volcano-tectonic (rifts, TF & fracture zones)	electricity production production of cold	3 stages approach	public enterprises / private investors
3	Western branch of the East African Rift System and Southern Rifts		convective systems active tectonic related	shallow medium enthalpy	simplified 3 stages approach	regional & local stakeholders
4	Deep reservoirs from sedimentary basins		sedimentary reservoir normal gradient	deep low enthalpy	data synthesized from oil exploration	answer local demand for DU
5	North Africa (Mediterranean collision zone)		thermal convection in folded Mesozoic cover	shallow low enthalpy	regional geology & local detailed studies	Public enterprises /private investors
6	Oceanic and continental mantle plumes (Comoros, Cap Verde, Darfur)		volcano hosted high enthalpy systems	electricity production	3 stages approach	public enterprises / private investors
7	Oceanic fracture zones off-shore & on land (Cameroon line)		volcano hosted medium-high enthalpy systems	electricity production	3 stages approach	public enterprises / private investors
8	hot-springs & heat anomalies from basement discontinuities		fault related convective systems	Direct Uses, SPA	shallow drilling near emergences	local developers
9	Deep EGS		various geological environments	cascade uses	deep drilling, expensive option	specialized enterprises
10	Ground Heat Pumps (12-24°C average)		any geological environment	direct uses (heat & cold)	various sizes & options (ground heat exchangers)	various (individual, community)

Figure 1: The 10 geothermal play types proposed for Africa

2. The play types proposed

The geothermal play-types proposed are based for 8 of the on the geodynamic environments encountered in Africa. The 2 lasts are not related to a single kind of resource and can be developed in any geological environment:

- 1: Eastern branch of the East African Rift System;
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- 4: Deep reservoirs from sedimentary basins;
- 5: North Africa (Mediterranean collision zone);
- 6: Oceanic and continental mantle plumes (Comoros, Cap Verde, Darfur);
- 7: Oceanic fracture zones off-shore & on land (Cameroon line);
- 8: hot-springs & heat anomalies from basement discontinuities;
- 9: Deep EGS;
- 10: Ground Heat Pumps (GHP) for heating and cooling.

The East African Rift System (EARS) play types (N° 1, 2 & 3)

The African continent is crossed by a major, exceptional geodynamic structure, which is unique on the planet Earth: The East African Rift System (EARS). An active plate boundary, although not having reached the stage of continental separation with the production of sea-floor spreading. A progressive increase of the spreading rate, from 1 to 6 mm/year is observed from south (Lake Tanganyika) to north (Northern extremity of the Main Ethiopian Rift (MER) due to the slow motion of the Somalia plate towards East (Figure 2).

1. Play-type N°1: Eastern branch of the East African Rift System

The Eastern branch of the EARV, crossing through Eritrea, Djibouti, Ethiopia, Kenya and Tanzania is the most spectacular, as plateaus at high altitude, with developed agricultural areas, thanks to favourable climatic conditions (periodical rainfalls), border up with a low-land valley where active volcanic and tectonic conditions favour the development of high temperature geothermal sites. These are particularly dominant in places where large volcanic units developed along local discontinuities of the rift system (fracture zones creating transform fault zones between spreading segments) (Figure 3).

Figure 2 (Left): The East African Rift system, with major fault systems (in red), major earthquake location (white dots for $M > 5$), manifestations of Quaternary volcanism (in yellow) and plate-motion vectors with GPS velocities (black arrows, with numbers in mm/y). Observe the progressive increase of the spreading rate from South to North along the EARV (from 2mm/y in the KRV5 to 7 mm/y along the MER and up to 2 cm/y in Afar). After Calais (2016).

Figure 3 (Right): Map of the volcanoes along the EARS. While only a few are located along the western branch, the eastern branch (MER and KRV) is characterized by the high number of volcanic centres (red triangles are quaternary volcanoes). *Map from*; www.riftvolc.geos.ed.ac.uk.

As a result, with an average interval of 40 to 60 km coinciding with sites of Quaternary volcanism, in the Kenyan Rift valley (KRV) and Main Ethiopian Rift (MER), high temperature sites allow for large-sized plants to produce power feeding the electrical grid. But so far, only a few of them have been explored and even less produce power as yet (Figure 4). These sites are characterised by shallow magma chambers – frequently related to calderas and recent silicic domes - and the development of reservoir conditions at temperatures of 150 to more than 300°C, thanks to fractured brittle rocks at depth of 1,000 to 3,500 metres, covered by an impermeable clay cap (Figure 5). Olkaria and Menengai in Kenya are references for such sites, allowing for large-size electric power production serving the grid.

Figure 4 Left : Geothermal sites for electricity production identified in Kenya (KRV), and Right: Status of Geothermal Exploration and Development in Ethiopia (Omenda, 2018; Kebede, 2016).

Figure 5: Schematic model for the play-type 1 text-book high temperature geothermal system, allowing for large-size electricity production serving the national grid), with its 3 components: the magmatic hat source (in red), the reservoir and the clay cap. The natural water refilling of the reservoir (blue arrows) and the hydrothermal up-flow (red arrows) is also pictured.

Note that – as seen in Figure 2 - the spreading rate increases from South to North, and therefore higher geothermal conditions will progressively be encountered from Southern Tanzania to the Northern part of the MER. Besides these large geothermal systems of high economic value, normal faults and open fissures allow for convective systems to develop at other sites, with hot-springs (Figure 6), or even steam vents at the surface (Figure 7). With the capture of the fluid at the surface, or better through shallow drilling, small plants will allow for Direct Use Geothermal Developments (DUGD), answering local socio-economic needs and various kinds of developments described below (see Geothermal Village concept) with minimal investments costs.

Figure 6: hot-springs along fault bordering lake Bogoria (Kenya). The site, where hydrothermal deposits developed, is an active ecosystem attracting fishes and flamingos (Photo J.Varet, 2013)

Figure 7: Steaming fault affecting a rhyolite flow near Olkaria, Kenya (Photo J.Varet, 2014).

As a whole, play-type 1 allows for 3 types of environments and developments:

- High temperature large-size geothermal sites, with direct-uses applications using the brine produced after steam separation and before re-injection;
- Medium-temperature local developments along active fissures affecting the rift floor away from the volcanic centres;
- Along normal faults bordering the rift system, particularly within marginal grabens as observed all along the Nubian escarpment in Ethiopia (Figure 8).

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Figure 8: Left: Google map showing the limit of the Nubian plateau: on the right (West) the Nile hydrographic basin, on the left (East) the Afar depression and the Awash River basin (Ethiopia), Marginal grabens developed along the escarpment. Location of major hot-springs sites, circa 100°C (from North to South: Harbu, Shekla, Borkena and Shewa Robit) are shown in yellow. Also shown the nearest steam vents s2.9 ex.ites in the Afar depression (in red). The limit of the Amhara and Afar regional states is also drawn (white dotted lines). Right: Geological interpretative section of the hydrogeological system feeding the geothermal systems (respectively hot-springs and steam vents) in the marginal graben - affecting the pre-Miocene “basement” made here of trap-basalts from the Nubian plateau - and Southern Afar volcanic ranges built along faults and dikes of NNE-SSW (MER) direction. Appropriate geophysical methodology are being developed to properly map in 3D the convective geothermal plumbing system to be tapped by shallow drilling for local developments.

Play-type N°2 : Oceanic Rifts: Red-Sea, Gulf of Aden and Afar

Due to the separation of Arabian plate from Africa, the best developed parts of this play-type, which are also the most active, are located along oceanic spreading axis of the Gulf of Aden and the Red Sea. Unfortunately, they are mainly submarine and not exploitable in present technological conditions. However, on land, all along the side of these two oceanic rifts, favourable geothermal conditions are found thanks to convective systems developed along normal faults and fracture zones. Thermal springs are found all along the Red Sea shore in Egypt (Gulf of Suez margins), Sudan, Eritrea, and along the Gulf of Aden in Djibouti as well as in Somaliland. They should allow for local geothermal development based on medium-low temperature applications. Such sites are already identified and under study in Egypt, like Ayun Musa and Hammam Faraun on the eastern coast, or Ain El Sukhna on the western coast of the Gulf of Suez (Lashin, 2015), as well as in Somaliland, as at Biyo Kulule near Bosano (Figure 9).

The Afar triangle displays specific geodynamic conditions as it does not result only from the slow-spreading separation of the Nubian and Somalian plates, but from the respective separation of the Arabian plate from Africa (as seen in Figure 10). With a much higher spreading rate of circa 2 cm a year, compared to 2 mm a year in the KRV. In this area (found in Ethiopia, Eritrea and Djibouti), the Mid-Oceanic-Ridge (MOR) system, elsewhere found at the bottom of the ocean floor, is exceptionally emerged enabling the existence of very remarkable geothermal conditions that are found on earth in only one other place: Iceland, but with a rather different climate. The whole Afar depression is rather arid due to a very low pluviosity compared with nearby plateaus, but these nearly “MOR” conditions favours the development of high temperature geothermal sites along the Axial Volcanic Ranges

described by Barberi and Varet (1972, 1975), where the tectonic, volcanic and hydrothermal activity concentrates, but also within central silicic volcanic systems developed at the favor of transverse fracture zones and transform fault zones (Varet, 2018; Varet et al., 2020).

Figure 9: Geological map of the surroundings of the Gulf of Aden, along the Yemen and Somalia coastal margins, showing the link of the geology on both sides, the spreading segments with magnetic anomalies increasing in age from both sides of the ridge axis, cut by transform faults and fracture zones (FZ) extending inside the continents (Omenda & Varet, unpublished, modified from Ali and Watts, 2013). In orange is shown the NE-SW FZ that determine the discontinuity east of Bossano (blue star). Biyu Kulul sits at the intersection of this NE-SW FZ with the WNW-ESE grabens parallel to the spreading axis.

Figure 10: Geological sketch map of the Afar triangle (Ethiopia, Eritrea, Djibouti, after CNR-CNRS, 1973; Varet, 1975; Beyene & Abdelsalam, 2005, modified) showing the location of the volcanic units of Afar (from Miocene to present). Magmatic geothermal sites develop all along the Afar floor, in the axial ranges, oriented NNW-SSE and NW-SE, as well as in marginal centres and transverse units. Similarly, along the Main Ethiopian Rift (observed here in SW Afar), the recent activity concentrated in basaltic fissural lava fields and central silicic volcanoes along NNE-SSW faults and dikes.

In addition, all along the Afar floor as well as its Nubian margin, amagmatic geothermal systems (steam vents on the floor and hot springs on the foot of the escarpment) develop along normal faults and open fissures, suitable for various kinds of DUGD including electricity generation through ORCs. Such various geothermal conditions – and related kinds of geothermal sites - are found in Eritrea along the axis of the Gulf of Zula and at Alid, as well as in Nabro caldera which is part of the Bidu-Dubbi transform fault zone. These are even more developed in the Afar Regional State, and bordering Regional States of Tigray and Amhara of Ethiopia. They also occur in the Djibouti Republic, along the margins of the Gulf of Tadjourah and the extension of the Aden ridge inland at Asal-Ghoubbet and Manda Inakir, as well as in many non-magmatic but active tectonic sites in the Western part of the country (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Geothermal sites in the Republic of Djibouti. Magmatic sites located along active spreading axis, whereas a-magmatic sites are shown with circles. The base map is the Geological Map of Central and Southern Afar (Varet, 1975), The two magmatic sites of Manda Inakir (North) and Abhé (South) could benefit from a joint investigation with Ethiopia as they extend on both sides of the border. But on Djibouti side alone, possibilities of DGUD exist in all sites. Map established by Géo2D for ODDEG (2018)

In the otherwise arid and apparently poor land, geothermal resources are so abundant that they should become solution of resilience, providing both DUGD options and drinking water for this pastoralist society deeply affected by climate change. Noting that, all over Afar, except along the Awash River basin, water is frequently more available in the form of steam vents than liquid spring and is currently used as such through traditional devices.

Play-type N°3: Western branch of the East African Rift System and Southern Rifts

As shown by Omenda et al. (2016), the geothermal conditions along the Western and Southern branches of the EARS radically differ from the ones prevailing in the Eastern branch. This is due to rather different lithospheric and geodynamic conditions underlined earlier by Barberi et al. (1982) and Demissie (2010). In fact, the Western branch affects an older, much thicker & more rigid lithosphere (Figure 12). This results in a dominantly tectonic behaviour, shown by a much stronger seismic activity than in the Eastern branch (Figure 13), with rare volcanic units producing magmas issued from deep-seated mantle with

limited settlements in magma chambers and rare occurrence of differentiated products, hence lack of geothermal heat source.

Figure 12 (Left): Distribution of alkaline rocks, carbonatites, and kimberlites in Mesozoic to Cenozoic rifts overprinting the velocity structure of cratonic blocks of Africa. Low velocities in blue to black, high velocities in red to white. Blue polygons = rifts; white asterisks = volcanoes; green stars = carbonatites; pink circles = nepheline syenites; white squares = kimberlites. CVL: Cameroon Volcanic Line. S-wave velocity (V_s) image is in the 100- to 175-km depth slice (from Begg et al. 2009, in Varet, 2018)

Figure 13 (Right): Map showing the seismic activity in Eastern Africa, with earthquakes recorded over a few decades; the size of the dots corresponds to the magnitude of the quake. Observe the much higher seismicity along the western branch of the EARS compared with the eastern one. (map from <http://hudsonvalleygeologist.blogspot.com/>).

This kind of geothermal system, controlled by hydrothermal convective circulations along normal faults in zones of extension allow for low to medium temperatures, hence are essentially suitable for DUGD. However, some of the rift zones display – eventually recurrent - magmatic diking along their axis. This for example, is the case for Lake Kivu where gases of mantellic origin are produced from deep sources on the lake floor (Rutagarama & Varet, 2018), as well as the active volcanic axis linking Lake Kivu with Nyiragongo volcano along the DRC-Rwanda border (Varet, 2018). A new eruption along this axis in may 2021 confirmed this hypothesis.

As a whole, along the Southern and Western branches of the East African Rift System (EARS), convective systems across normal faults are the targets to be searched for geothermal development of Direct Use (DU) kind. This will generally concern faulted systems, with permeability zones resulting from the faults themselves, but may also concern sedimentary strata with good permeability. The knowledge of such systems may advantageously result from oil exploration, which targets such layers. In the case of Uganda, in addition to thermal springs along normal faults bordering the lakes, geothermal reservoirs

of interest have been identified as sub-products of the geoscientific investigations by the oil industry. These are suited for direct uses (medium to low temperature applications).

Figure 14: Block diagram showing the model proposed by Chakrabarti et al. (2009) for the Virunga volcanics in the western rift, compared to the eastern rift. Nyiragongo lavas are shown to issue from 150 Km deep in the mantle without differentiation, whereas in the eastern rift, magma production and differentiation occur at much shallower depth in a thinned continental crust (Varet, 2018).

Figure 15: A-magmatic convective geothermal play system in active extensional terrains with different types of reservoirs. Type 1 is an upflow zone, with convection cell from infiltration to discharge along one fault. Temperature gradient is gradually increasing at well site 1. Type 2a and 2B are outflow zones, fault leakage-controlled plays. The temperature gradient of a well drilled into such an area rises up to the permeable layer and drops below the layer (well 2a and 2b). (Moeck, 2014)

Lay-type N°4 Geothermal resources from sedimentary basins

In the above descriptions, we focused on geothermal systems linked with geodynamically active areas, where convective systems develop thanks to active tectonic or magmatic conditions, with resulting high heat flow. There are however other possibilities for geothermal applications in regions of sedimentary basins, with average normal gradient conditions, but where the stratigraphic sequence allows for permeable formations to develop, for instance karstic limestones or unsealed sandstones or conglomerates. Sedimentary basins

cover large parts of the African continent (nearly the half of it, as seen in Figure 1), and such favourable conditions for utilization of geothermal energy in normal gradient areas are met in various locations of the continent, including in particular its western, central and northern parts, but also many coastal areas. Besides direct production from deep aquifers, geological features like salt domes, anticlines, or faults, these sedimentary basins will display hot-spring discharges along such discontinuities. Such geothermal opportunities (allowing for production of low temperature fluids and related applications) have been reported in Cameroon, Nigeria, Tanzanian coast, North and South Africa, among others. The geological knowledge and understanding of these areas at depth frequently results from the oil exploration, with geological and geophysical (in particular seismic) surveys allowing to develop 3D models at regional scale, and consequently to ascertain geothermal resources over wide areas. Such conditions allow for development of DGUD projects with limited risks, hence economic developments despite moderate geothermal gradient conditions.

Two examples were studied recently in eastern Tanzania and central Nigeria. In both cases, the stratigraphic sequence is well established, with identified aquifers at depth forming low-temperature geothermal reservoirs, and structural conditions allowing for higher temperatures to occur thanks to hydrothermal convection along horst-and-graben, salt domes or anticline structures. For example, in the case of Luhoi, in eastern Tanzania (Kajugus, 2018) it is a horst structure underlying a permeable sedimentary layer (the Kipatimu sandstone) which allow for emergences at the temperature of 72°C, with the possibility to reach up to 100°C at a depth of circa 1 km (Figure 16). In Nigeria and other countries surrounding basins of central western Africa, the geothermal investigations summarized by Kwaya et al. (2019) shows the control of the Tertiary and Cretaceous rifts on the geothermal gradient at the scale of the regional sedimentary basins (Figure 17). These studies show potential geothermal applications for direct uses at wide scale in all Africa's sedimentary basins.

Figure 16: Conceptual model of the Luhoi geothermal system in Eastern Tanzania shown with an idealised NW-SE section showing the Kipatimu sandstone host of the geothermal reservoir, with a horst structure which controls the hydrogeology and consequent thermal convection. The diagram on the right show how the convection increase the geothermal gradient in the first kilometre at depth. (Armadillo et al. 2020).

Figure 17: Some geological characteristics of the sedimentary basins in Nigeria and surrounding countries showing the structures at depth, particularly the underlying tertiary and cretaceous rifts determining the thermal gradients (A: left) and some details of the Nigeria part of the Sokoto basin (B: right) showing the resulting thermal gradients on a simplified geological base map (from Kwaya et al., 2019).

An efficient tool for the promotion of such geothermal developments is to publish synthesis documents (maps, sections and reports) showing the geothermal resources existing at depth, with precision of their extension, geometry, thickness, permeability, temperature and composition of the reservoir rocks and of the contained fluids (Figure 18). Such information systems should be handled at national and regional scale and made available to the public through relevant Geological Survey Organisation (GSO). Such information was for example published in France by BRGM (French GSO) for all the sedimentary basins in the 1970's (Varet, 1978, 1982, 1985), and made accessible on line¹ for the use of any party interested to develop a project of exploitation of the resource available at depth at any place. This public initiative played a major role in the successful deployment in the country, with 300.000 housing turning from fossil fuel to geothermally heat in the period 1976-1986.

Play-type N°5 : North Africa (Mediterranean collision zone)

In the Mediterranean active seismic zones of North Africa: in Algeria, Morocco, Libya, Egypt and Tunisia, where anomalous thermal zones are known and have been utilized since time immemorial (Greek and Roman baths, Arabic Hammams notably, Fig. 2.29 & 2.30). Several of them have been modernised into thermal stations curing various diseases. In addition, new developments were engaged, in Tunisia and Algeria (Saibi, 2015), for other direct uses applications including green housing and aquaculture (see § 5.3 and 6.3 for achievements and government support). This allowed the production of vegetables at very competitive prices, covering both local needs and exports to Europe.

¹ See for instance : <https://www.geothermies.fr/viewer/?extent=-48060.0839%2C5924786.9364%2C416065.5518%2C6138810.6156&al=region/>

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Figure 18: Simplified maps of the major geothermal parameters for a geothermal reservoir: the case of the Dogger, a marine limestone Jurassic layer of Paris basin now widely used for DGUD applications since it was published as open public atlas by BRGM and ELF in 1976. The parameters surveyed are: 1: Depth, 2: Temperature, 3. Permeability, 4. Thickness, 5. Lithology and 6: Salinity. From J.Varet, 1985.

Figure 19: (A) Thermal springs of Hammam Meskoutine in Algeria, emerging at a temperature of 97 °C, with a flow rate of 1 650 l/s. (B) A modern thermal station was built at a place already exploited for therapeutic bathes since Roman times.

Figure 20: Traditional Hammam (thermal station) of Bouhadjar (Algeria)

Play-type N°6 : Oceanic and continental mantle plumes (ex.: Comoros & Darfur)

At the location of oceanic (around Africa) or intra-continental mantle plumes:

- in the Indian Ocean (Comoros, Réunion, where geothermal projects are being considered),
- in the Atlantic (Cape Verde volcanic Islands), or
- in the continent (as for example. Darfur in Sudan where an area of 100 km x 50 km is covered by basaltic flows and pyroclastic deposits ranging from basanite to trachyte with a volcanic activity ranging from late Miocene to Holocene, and the most recent eruptions dated to $4,900 \pm 520$ y bp. Preliminary studies have been undertaken in the Darfur area which confirmed potential existence of viable geothermal systems.

Play-type N°7: Extension of Atlantic Ocean fracture zones off-shore and on land

This play-type is typically expressed by the Sao Tome - Cameroon line, which links the Mid-Atlantic Ridge to Sao Tome Islands and extends North-East (NE) across the continent, an area not really explored yet for its geothermal potential (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Map showing the distribution of the Cameroon Volcanic Line magmatism in the continent and its extension off-shore including oceanic islands (Sao Tome, Principe, Bioko) and sea mounts (Tefogoum et al., 2017).

Play-type N°8: Hot-springs & local heat anomalies resulting from basement discontinuities

Such local geothermal sites may occur in most African countries, notably in south Africa (Figure 22) or eastern RDC (Figure 23), thanks to specific tectonic (faults, folds) and geological discontinuities (permeable/impermeable contacts of rock formations), i.e. conditions that favour ground-water thermal convection.

Figure 22 (Left). Hot springs of South Africa. Very hot springs (above 50°C) are found in the Limpopo Province in the North and in the Western Cape Province in the South West of the country. From Nyabeze et al. (2015).

Figure 23 (Right): Map of geothermal sources of the eastern part of the DRC (from Makuku, 2019).

The last two play-types do not rely primarily on the geodynamic environment of the site, as these geothermal options are meant to adjust to any geological environments thanks to engineering solutions at resource level. Two cases can be distinguished there: Deep Engineered Geothermal Systems (Deep EGS) and use of the shallow sub-soil with Ground Heat Pumps (GHP).

Play-type N°9: Engineered Deep Geothermal Systems (EGS) may be developed in Africa in the future, once most favourable experiences presently being developed in Europe, and particularly in Germany, will have encountered both technical and economic success. These are in fact rather expensive options (due to deep drilling and engineering at depth, which require highly specialized enterprises).

Play-type N°10: Ground Heat Pumps (GHP) are tapping superficial resources (a few meters to a few hundred meters deep) at temperatures of $12-24^{\circ}\text{C}$ (average). They may be engaged in any geological environment, and are suitable for various direct uses (DU) applications (heat & cold). The use of GHP for cooling is particularly well suited for Africa where air conditioning may absorb a large part of the electricity consumption (as it is the case in Djibouti, f.i.). This technology also adapts to various sizes (individual, community, tertiary) and options (water wells of ground heat exchangers).

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